

THERMO-MECHANICAL BENEFITS OF A RIGID INSULATION LAYER ON IRON AND STEEL LADLE SHELL LIFESPAN

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ABSTRACT

Iron & Steel ladles are used as transport and/or treatment vessels during the metallurgical process. The ladle shell is designed to withstand various thermal and mechanical loading cycles. As shown by a combination of thermal modeling, finite element analysis and damage analysis, the formation of cracks in the vicinity of weldments of ArcelorMittal Burns Harbor ladles is related to creep damage. The addition of a rigid insulation board in the refractory lining dramatically improves the lifespan of the ladle shell thanks to consistent lower shell temperatures. The rigid insulation board helps to preserve the integrity of the shell even if previously used without any insulation.

INTRODUCTION

ArcelorMittal Burns Harbor experienced some crack formation at different locations of steel ladle shells. This type of damage can be related to different sources including fatigue and creep. The temperatures measured on the ladle shells used to be close, if not higher than the recommended maximum service temperature of the steel grade used for the body of the shell. The introduction of a rigid insulation board in the refractory lining has dramatically reduced the shell temperatures.

A numerical simulation has been developed to study the effects of the shell temperature reduction on the damage mechanisms leading to the crack formation observed in the plant. The first step of the modeling is to confirm the thermal profiles of the ladle shells in operations with and without the rigid insulation board. The second step is to estimate the stress levels during the different stages of the process and identify the worse conditions for the ladle shell. Non-linear material models are introduced in the thermo-mechanical behavior of the refractory lining. The variations of the fatigue and cumulative creep damage are then estimated for both lining configurations with and without the rigid insulation board. The benefit of the rigid insulation board on the shell lifespan is highlighted thanks to the estimation of the cumulative damage in the shell.

PROCESS OVERVIEW

At ArcelorMittal Burns Harbor, the heat cycle starts at the ladle vertical re-heater. The steel ladle is then moved to one of the basic oxygen furnaces for tapping. Once full of molten metal, the 275mt ladle follows a standard 'treatment station/degasser (if required)/caster' process route. The residence time for the molten steel in the ladle is about 150min/heat. The heat-to-heat cycle for a ladle is about 300min. The design of the ladle is fully reproduced in a commercial modeling software (Fig.1).

Fig. 1: Shell design used in the 3D thermal and fatigue models.

The ladle shell is 5.1m high and 4.6m in diameter. The ladle shells have been in operations for about 20 years. The steel grade used for the body of the shells is a carbon-molybdenum alloy grade recommended for high temperature application (UNS K11820). The steel grade used for the stiffener bands is a carbon grade used for pressure vessel (UNS K02100).

The two main crack locations are in the vicinity of weldments between the two stiffener bands, and at the level of the bottom inner plate. Such crack formations are shown in Figure 2.

Fig.2: Example of a vertical crack below the top stiffener band (left), and of a horizontal crack at the bottom level (right)

The working lining is relined about 10 times per ladle shell per year. The life of the working lining is 80 heats. The life of the working lining represents a complete thermal cycle for the shell with the addition of the preheating stage. During that complete cycle, the ladle is either stationary on a ladle stand or moving along the process route hanging on the hooks of the crane. This represents about 7,000 mechanical cycles per year; where a cycle includes one stand position and one hook position.

The refractory lining is composed of a 203mm MgO-C brick as working lining in the slagzone area and a 127mm AMC brick as working lining in the barrel area, a 64mm 60% Al₂O₃ brick as safety lining, and a 12.7mm dense forsteritic material as insulation layer. The rigid insulation board primarily reduces the thermal loss through the ladle walls. It is also used in strategies to improve the process control. Compared to other insulation materials, the rigid board presents a unique set of thermo-mechanical properties for long term service in such a high stress-inducing application. The main characteristics are the well-balanced stiffness/elasticity ratio, and the good compromise between the thermal conductivity and mechanical strength at high temperature. The material also exhibits a resilient behavior and maintains its integrity under cyclic loads up to 7MPa (Fig.3).

Fig.3: Resilience behavior of the rigid insulation material after 3 cycles up to 7MPa at 500°C.

The integrity of the rigid insulation board and stability of its thermo-mechanical properties have been previously confirmed through shell temperature measurements on ladles up to 175,000 cast tons per insulation lining.^[1] Laboratory testing also highlighted the stability of the thermal conductivity throughout the life of the material in service. The stability of the material in service is definitely a major benefit for long term damage modeling such as creep and fatigue damage. The prediction for the thermo-mechanical behavior of the ladle shell in operations is then more reliable.

Using all the properties of the different materials including the steel grades for the shell as function of the temperature, the thermo-mechanical modeling of the ladle shell with the refractory lining is performed thanks to a commercial modeling software.

THERMO-MECHANICAL MODELING

To model the damage in the shell induced from the thermo-mechanical behavior of the shell and the refractory lining, the thermal and stress patterns have to be properly estimated throughout the life of the shell. The thermal loading is estimated including the conduction, the convection and the radiation mechanisms for the different surfaces of the ladle shell and the refractory lining when the ladle is empty and full of molten steel. The mechanical loading on the ladle shell is a mix of the loadings from the moving of the ladle during the metallurgical process, and from the thermal expansion of the refractory layers.

The thermal profile of a ladle shell has been firstly modeled thanks to a 3D computer fluid dynamics analysis. The thermal state of the ladle shell is established in steady state conditions for four different lining configurations. The two variables combined to get the four main thermal profiles are the thickness of the working lining (new or worn) and the use of the rigid insulation board (with or without). The calculated thermal profiles are then compared to thermal images of ladles in operations. The thermal images of full ladles are taken after a sufficient residence time so the ladle shell is considered in quasi-steady state conditions. The same approach is applied for empty ladles so the thermal profile is considered steady. Figure 4 compares the thermal profile of a ladle shell calculated for the 'worn/with' configuration to a thermal picture of a ladle with the same lining conditions.

Fig.4: Calculated thermal profile compared to the actual profile of a ladle in operations for the same lining configuration.

The average temperature for the mid-section of the sidewall area is respectively about 275°C and 342°C for the ladle lining with and without the rigid insulation board. The temperature difference between the two ladle linings is then about 67°C. The calculated profiles are then used to confirm the thermal loading of the ladle shell in the thermal FEA modeling module.

The mechanical loading on the ladle shell from transfer between the different stations of the steelmaking process are modeled directly in the FEA modeling module. The two loading modes, hooked or on stand, are simply set by selecting the points of loading.

The complexity of the whole ladle assembly including the refractory lining and the shell structure makes it difficult to directly assess the realistic thermo-mechanical loading of the shell from the refractory lining in the 3D model. A simpler 2D modeling is then performed to properly insert non-linear responses in the strain-stress relations of the refractory materials. Different sources of damage occur in the refractory layers during the life of the materials such as cracking and softening. Without taking into account such relaxation mechanisms, the magnitude of the stress levels predicted in the ladle shell and in the refractory lining are unrealistic. This is typically the case when a model is based on a linear thermo-elastic approach for the refractory lining. Different models have been developed to introduce the degradation of the physical properties of quasi-brittle materials during service.^[2] Because the timeline for the thermal cycling of the shell is a working lining campaign, the damage mechanism included in this 2D model is the creep behavior of the working lining layer only.

The 2D model is based on a quarter of the ladle assembly including the different refractory layers and the shell. The refractory lining is taken as new. The thermal profiles for both the ladle with and without the rigid insulation board are confirmed as the same as the profiles from the first 3D modeling. The thermo-mechanical behavior of the assembly is then calculated for up to 45 thermal cycles, representing 45 heats on the ladle assembly. The trend lines for the stress level in the ladle shell with and without the rigid insulation layer are then estimated in terms of heat cycles. Figure 5 shows a close-up of the thermal profile and of the hoop stress pattern at the end of the 43rd heat.

Fig.5: Thermal state (left) and hoop stress level (right) calculated during the cooling stage at the end of the 43rd heat of the ladle lining with the rigid insulation board.

The refractory layers are still in compression during this period of the cooling stage while the ladle shell is in tension. Because no relaxation mechanisms are considered for the safety lining material, the tensile stress level induced in the shell are expected to be less conservative than in the actual conditions.

The use of an insulation layer in a refractory lining generally increases the compressive stresses acting on the hot face of the working lining. Thanks to its compliance, the rigid insulation board helps to decrease those stresses. The stress estimated on the hot face of the working lining is actually at the same level for both lining configurations. However, the higher thermal load of the refractory lining with the insulation board slightly increases the tensile stresses in the shell as already seen in similar modeling.^[3] The highest hoop stress level calculated in the ladle shell layer with the rigid insulation board is about 63MPa. The stress peak is reached after the first tap in a new lining. The stress level then decayed at every subsequent heat according to the creep law defined for the working lining material. The stress peak for the ladle shell without the rigid insulation board is about 55MPa. These stress levels confirm the well balanced selection of the rigid insulation board with a significant reduction of 67°C on the thermal profile of the shell, and with a slight increase of 8MPa for the stress peak induced in the shell by the refractory lining. The effects of the temperature and stress variations on the damage mechanisms in the ladle shell are then estimated thanks to a fatigue and creep damage analysis.

DAMAGE ANALYSIS

The ladle shell is obviously under different thermo-mechanical loading modes during a full thermal cycle as defined by the life of the refractory working lining. The failure mode is then composed by a mix of different damage mechanisms that are active at the same time. The three primary sources of damage are oxidation, fatigue and creep.^[4] The damage from each process is summed to obtain an estimate of the overall predicted life. However, one of the damage mechanisms is usually dominant. For the damage analysis, it means that the dominant damage mechanism has to be identified and that the other individual damage models must be properly defined for the conditions where the life is directly related to the dominant failure mechanisms.

The oxidation damage is not considered in this damage analysis since the observed shell temperatures are not in a high range.

The fatigue from mechanical-only and from thermal-only loadings are estimated for the 3D ladle model thanks to a numerical simulation module including in the FEA software. The life defined by the mechanical-only fatigue at room temperature is shown in Figure 6. The lowest life estimated for both ladle positions is larger than 10^9 cycles. It is located around the loading areas in both cases. The mechanical damage is not expected to vary dramatically for the temperature range estimated for both ladle configurations, with or without the rigid insulation board.^[5]

Fig.6: Life expectancy of the insulated ladle shell cyclically loaded on stand and hooked positions at room temperature.

The number of cycles estimated for the thermal-only fatigue is about 10^9 heats before failure in the areas of concern for both ladle configurations (Fig.7). The overall pattern for the thermal-only fatigue is more uniform for the insulated ladle shell.

Fig.7: Thermal fatigue for both ladle shell configurations; without the rigid board on the left, with the rigid board on the right.

Different time-temperature parameters exist to predict creep damage. Amongst those existing parameters, the Larson-Miller parameter (LMP) does not necessarily give conservative life predictions.^[6,7] It is nevertheless widely used in time to rupture analysis.

The LMP combines the temperature and the time of rupture as follow:

$$LMP = T * (\log t_r + C)$$

with T: the absolute temperature; t_r : the time of rupture; C: material and reaction dependent constant specific to the steel grade.^[8] C is taken equal to 19 for the grade used for the body of the ladle shell.^[9]

The stress dependence of the LMP can be described by the following polynomial form:

$$LMP = \alpha + \beta \log(\sigma) + \gamma \log^2(\sigma)$$

with the following values for the regression constants: $\alpha = 13108$, $\beta = 3647$, $\gamma = -1408$.

The master curve giving time to rupture depending on stress and temperature for the body steel grade is then calculated.

To take into account the effect of the welded joints and heat affected zones on creep failure assessment, a simple approach based on the introduction of a stress concentration factor is used to correct the stress levels around those areas. The stress factor is estimated according to the crack stress approach applied to cracks that are initiated along the weld toe.^[10]

The cumulative damage of pure creep is estimated by the Robinson's linear cumulative damage rule. Figure 8 shows the cumulative damage for the areas around welded joints during one thermal cycle defined as one campaign of working lining.

Fig.8: Cumulative creep damage for one working lining campaign. The right and the left scales are for the lining with and without the rigid insulation board respectively.

The cumulative creep damage around the welded joints and heat affected zones for the ladle shell with and without the rigid insulation board is about 8.10^{-5} and 6.10^{-3} respectively. Creep is definitely the dominant damage mechanism compared to thermal and mechanical fatigue.

The creep damage is more than 70 times smaller for the ladle shell with the rigid insulation board. The simple addition of the rigid insulation board dramatically increase the life expectancy of the shell. The benefits of the measured and calculated shell temperature reduction are more significant than the stress increase in the early life of the working lining.

Furthermore, the use of the rigid insulation board helps to spread the creep damage over a longer period of the thermal cycle. 75% of the creep damage is accumulated within the first 30 heats of the working lining without insulation. The number of heats to reach the same proportion of creep damage is almost doubled for the lining with the insulation. The use of the insulation layer then decreases the strain rate and the creep damage is more evenly distributed till the end of the lining campaign. At the same time, the impact of the preheating stage on the shell damage is lowered.

With creep really dictating the damage in the shell, no fatigue-creep interaction are considered for the total damage as a preliminary modeling. The total damage for the ladle shell can then be estimated by the sum of the Miner's linear cumulative damage for the pure fatigue term and the Robinson's cumulative damage as the pure creep term. The cumulative damage for the areas around welded joints of ladle shell without the rigid insulation board gives an estimated life of about 16 years. The use of the rigid insulation board cut the creep damage by a magnitude of almost 2. Creep damage is no longer a concern in regards to the expected lifespan of the shell. The objective for this shell is not to predict its remaining life anymore, but to further find the optimal conditions to preserve its integrity as long as possible.

The benefits of the rigid insulation board are still significant for ladle shells with many years of service without insulation. Figure 9 presents the benefits of the rigid insulation board on the lifespan of ladle shells with different number of years in service before the addition of the insulation layer.

Fig.9: Cumulative creep and fatigue damage for shells after different number of years in service before the use of the insulation layer.

In addition to the benefits of the rigid insulation board on the lifespan of the shell, the reduction of the shell temperature will help to reduce the deformation of the ladle shell, hence lower maintenance costs and easier refractory installation. The bulging on the bottom area of the sidewalls is commonly observed on shell operated without insulation (Fig.10).

Fig.10: View of the bulging area on the lower sidewall of a shell compared to the calculated profile without insulation.

CONCLUSION

The formation of cracks has been observed in specific areas of ArcelorMittal Burns Harbor's ladle shells. The ladle shell were previously operated at temperatures close to the maximum service temperature recommended for the steel grade used for the body of the shell, if not higher. A thermal modeling, a finite element analysis and damage analysis applied to the whole ladle assembly in operations have been combined to identify the dominant damage mode. The lifespan of the ladle shell used without an efficient insulation layer against high shell temperature is definitely shortened compared to its expected life by creep damage.

Because of its specific physical and mechanical properties, the rigid insulation board offers a well-balanced thermo-mechanical solution against high shell temperature. The cumulative damage analysis confirms the reduction of the shell temperature has dramatically improved the lifespan of the ladle shell. The slight stress increase induced in the shell as a response to the higher thermal loading of the refractory lining is definitely overcome by the benefit of the lower shell temperature.

The occurrence of the crack formation is related to the presence of welded joints and heat affected zones. A detailed analysis of the stress concentration factor for such areas with the modeling software would help to ascertain if the current model is conservative or not. A metallography analysis of the crack morphology and the steel material around the crack would also confirm the lack of interaction between the different damage mechanisms.

The addition of the rigid insulation board to the regular refractory lining is beneficial not only for process control like the reduction of the temperature drop of the molten steel, but also for process improvement like a dramatic increase of the shell lifespan, a better ladle availability and a higher safety in operations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Yong L, Kumar S, Bradley J, Rebouillat L, Roy N. Improvement of thermal efficiency in steel ladles. Goski DG, Smith JD, editors. UNITECR 2013: Proceedings of the Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories; 2013 Sep 10-13; Victoria, Canada. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, NJ; 2014. P. 345-50.
- [2] Allix O, Hild F. Continuum damage mechanics of materials and structures. Elsevier Science Ltd, Paris (France). 2002.
- [3] Jin S, Gruber D, Harmuth H, Fréchet M-H. Thermomechanical steel ladle simulation including a Mohr-Coulomb plasticity failure model. RHI Bulletin. 2012; 1, 39-43.
- [4] Sehitoglu H. Thermo-mechanical fatigue life prediction methods. In: Mitchell MR, Landgraf RW, editors. Advances in fatigue lifetime predictive techniques. ASTM STP1122. American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia. 1992, 47-76.
- [5] Pense AW, Stout RD. Elevated temperature fatigue of pressure vessel steels. Weld Res Sup. 1975; 8, 247s-52s.
- [6] Tamura M, Esaka H, Shinozuka K. Applicability of an Exponential Law in Creep of Metals. Mat. Trans. 2003; 44 (1), 118-26.
- [7] Seruga D, Fajdiga M, Nagode M. Creep damage calculation for thermo mechanical fatigue. J Mech Eng. 2011; 57(5), 371-8.
- [8] Larson FR, Miller EJ. Time-temperature relationship for rupture and creep stresses. Trans. ASME. 1952; 74, 765-75.
- [9] Tamura M, Abe F, Shiba K, Sakasegawa H, Tanigawa H. Larson-Miller constant of heat-resistant steel. Metall Mater Trans A. 2013; 44A(6), 2645-61.
- [10] Radaj D, Sonsino CM, Fricke W. Fatigue assessment of welded joints by local approaches. 2nd edition. Woodhead Publishing Limited. 2006, 660p.